

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ENVIRONMENTAL RISK AS A PROBLEM FOR THE SOCIO-
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF THE REGION****Anatoly Pozmogov¹, Boris Kallagov¹, Zalina Tedeeva^{1,2}, Marina Kuchieva¹,
Alena Gergaeva³**

¹Finance University under the Government of the Russian Federation, Vladikavkaz branch, 7 Molodozhnaya str., Vladikavkaz 362002, Russia, ²North Ossetian State University, Vatutina str., 44, Vladikavkaz 362025, Russia, ³Vladikavkaz Institute of Management, Borodinskaya str., 14, Vladikavkaz 362025, Russia.

Article Received: January 2019**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

The environmental situation in many regions of the country, including in the North Caucasus Federal District, remains rather complicated today. An analysis of the ecological situation in the whole of the North Caucasus Federal District allows us to conclude that the current environmental problems in the region are, firstly, environmental pollution by products of human activity, manifested in the release of hazardous substances into the atmosphere by industrial enterprises and road transport and the result of discharge of untreated sewage into the rivers of the Terek-Caspian basin; and the second no less serious environmental problem in the region remains - depletion of natural resources as a result of economic and other activities: erosion, increased acidity and soil salinity; inefficient and wasteful use of water resources (primarily freshwater), deforestation and the disappearance of many plant and animal species. According to the authors, at present, in the North Caucasus Federal District, as well as in the Russian Federation in general, there is an acute need for the development and application of a new concept of ecological thinking with a mechanism for its substantive implementation that is adequate to the new challenges of our time and is capable of ensuring the basic constitutional right of our country's citizens environmental safety.

Keywords: *environmental risks, waste disposal, water pollution, environmental crime, reasonable self-restraint, social advertising.*

Corresponding author:**Anatoly Pozmogov,**

Finance University under the Government of the Russian Federation,
Vladikavkaz branch, 7 Molodozhnaya str., Vladikavkaz 362002, Russia.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Anatoly Pozmogov et al., *Environmental Risk As A Problem For The Socio-Economic Development Of The Region.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(03).

INTRODUCTION:

The realities of the dynamic development of modern Russian society are focused on the paradigm of sustainable development. And not the last link in this chain is the issue of environmental safety and minimization of environmental risks.

The concept of environmental safety, despite its widespread use in the legislative array and its "popularity" in the scientific community, still does not have a well-established definition in the ideological and methodological aspects. Environmental safety is interpreted as:

- the state of security of the relevant objects;
- a system of measures and norms, the sum of conditions that eliminate a specific risk or threat;
- the degree of security of its object [1].

At the same time, as a rule, environmental safety is assigned the role of a "fixer" of a separate environmental legal segment.

For Russia, with its territorial state organization unique in its complexity, a balanced and balanced regional policy is necessary, including in the field of environmental management and environmental safety. It should ultimately lead to an increase in the level and quality of life, an integral part of which is a human-friendly environment [2].

Until recently, it was believed that environmental management as a specific type of activity cannot be based on industry principles, including management in this area. However, in our opinion, the dominant role in the implementation of the principles of economic policy in the country should also be played by natural environmental and economic, and not only strictly economic and administrative-territorial factors of development. In a federal state, regional policy in the field of environmental safety and environmental risk management is a key integrating component of a nationwide national security policy.

The ecological state of the subjects of the North Caucasus Federal District clearly demonstrates the common environmental threats peculiar to many regions of Russia (air pollution, water basins, the formation of industrial and household waste, soil degradation, reduction of forests, etc.).

However, there are some specific features and problems associated with minimizing environmental risks and threats, the most significant of which are as follows:

- liquidation of accumulated clinkers and tailing dumps after mineral processing in the region;
- anthropogenic pollution of surface and groundwater;
- problems associated with the management of municipal solid waste;
- the condition of the Terek-Caspian water basin;
- Egoistic human attitude toward the environment (environmental crime, corruption, indifference, etc.) [3].

The ecological situation in the Republic of North

Ossetia - Alania remains quite complicated at the present time. According to the environmental rating of the magazine Expert, RNO-Alania ranks 64th in the general federal list and last in 7th place in the North Caucasus Federal District. The main problem in the republic is the activity of the Electrozinc plant, which, by definition, is a serious environmental problem not only for the city of Vladikavkaz but also for several neighboring regions.

Experts cited depressing data on atmospheric pollution by factory emissions and environmental degradation in the city and in the region as a whole. The irresponsible attitude of the company's management and regional authorities to the problem was difficult to call a planned murder of the residents of their own republic. In turn, this led to the formation in RNO-Alania of a sufficiently influential civil wave of protest. As a result, the owner of the enterprise of the Ural Mining and Metallurgical Company decided to terminate the plant's activities in terms of the main production profile and create an engineering industry enterprise on its premises [4].

In addition to the problem, OJSC "Electrozinc" rather complicated environmental problems in RNO-Alania remain illegal logging, the virtually uncontrolled operation of groundwater resources, unsystematic attitude to agricultural land, to its own oil and gas resources.

And if the republic belongs in the Russian Federation to regions with a complex environmental situation, then one cannot recognize that the city of Vladikavkaz in this context is not a prosperous municipal entity; in addition, there are:

- air pollution (increase in the number of vehicles);
- deterioration of the quality of drinking water;
- reduction of park areas and green areas, especially in new housing estates;
- the increase in the number of filling stations, many of which have expired reservoirs of expiration dates and the leakage of petroleum products from them can adversely affect the groundwater that provides drinking water to people in the flat part of the republic;
- the level of environmental education of citizens [7].

As is well known Stavropol Territory - is one of the most fertile regions of Russia. At the same time, it should be noted that the ecological situation in the region is rather complicated, as evidenced by the fact that in the annual environmental rating of the Russian regions, the Stavropol region takes 41st place.

The main reason is the consumer and even predatory attitude towards natural resources, which over the past decades has led to the formation of poles of environmental distress in Stavropol Krai that negatively affect people's health and longevity. And on their territory live 26% of the population of the region. Especially unfavorable for a living is the regional center itself - Stavropol, as well as Nevinnomyssk, Kochubeevsky and Budenovsky districts. First of all,

the difficult situation with emissions of harmful substances by industrial enterprises into the atmosphere is of concern.

Statistics show: 85 kg per year per resident of Nevinnomyssk harmful substances entering the atmosphere from stationary sources of pollution. This indicator is slightly less in Budennovsk - 60 kg, in Minvody, it is 6 kg, in Stavropol - 9 kg. In addition to stationary sources, the atmosphere is polluted by motor vehicles, with the number of cars in the region increasing every year, and with it, the pollution of air in large cities also increases; the problems of waste disposal and pollution of water bodies in the region also remain extremely acute.

In addition to the above, it is advisable in our opinion to also identify other risk-forming environmental problems of the region:

- soil erosion - the destructive work of the flow of water and wind;
- over-moistening of lands - the fertile layer can be swamped;
- soil salinization and not only in areas of shallow salt-bearing rocks;
- desertification and the desiccation of land (the second is extremely negative);
- water and air pollution;
- the problem of the preservation of fauna and flora (the question of the preservation of various forms of life; deforestation and forest fires are a real misfortune here);
- The problem of biological pollution (insects, locust, Colorado potato beetle, varroa mite, ragweed, causing allergic reactions in humans).

The environmental problems of the Republic of Dagestan are no less complex and significant than in other regions of the federal district.

The most difficult environmental problem for the republic is the shortage of drinking water, as a significant number of water arteries in the region are polluted, and the water quality does not meet sanitary standards. Sources of water and large water bodies are clogged with household waste and sewage. There are cases when the flow channels are clogged by the population itself for selfish purposes.

The next risk-forming environmental problem in Dagestan is the problem of water disposal. Virtually all urban communication networks engaged in sewerage are thoroughly worn out and do not function effectively. The problem of environmental pollution, associated with waste management, also remains unresolved in the republic. Illegal landfills and landfills operate in almost all villages and towns. As a result, soil and groundwater pollution. The problem of land desertification remains extremely acute in the republic, as a result of unsystematic and selfish economic activities in the subject of the Federation [5].

Garbage dumps and unauthorized dumps remain a

serious risk-forming environmental problem for residents of almost all settlements in the North Caucasus. The Department for Economic and Social Policy of the Office of the Plenipotentiary Representative of the President of the Russian Federation to the North Caucasus Federal District in January 2018 provided disappointing statistics: out of more than 800 known landfills in the district, only 18 are included in the state register, i.e. considered authorized. In Ingushetia, for example, there are no such official facilities at all.

In all the subjects of the NCFD, there are regional waste disposal programs, but territorial schemes have not yet been developed anywhere. Rosprirodnadzor in 2018 revealed in the North Caucasus Federal District 1600 places of unauthorized disposal of municipal solid waste.

In the environmental rating of the country, the Kabardino-Balkarian Republic occupies a worthy 38th place, but this does not mean at all that the ecological situation here differs significantly from that in the neighboring regions of the federal district. Experts associate the current rather complex ecological situation in the republic, first of all, with the work of a large industrial enterprise, OAO Hydrometallurg. The regional leadership has repeatedly promised its own citizens to solve the problem, but to part with the disciplined taxpayer who annually pays more than 200 million rubles to the republic's budget, the officials are still lacking political will [6].

JSC "Gidrometallurg" is not the only environmental problem of the republic. Until recently, the problem of landfills, of which there are 112 in the republic, of which only two are officially listed in the state register of landfills, remains relevant. About 400 thousand tons of municipal solid waste is generated annually in the republic, and their amount is constantly increasing.

The problem of illegal logging, water pollution and the unsatisfactory condition of most of the burial grounds of cattle in the region also remain sufficiently risky economic problems.

The Kabardino-Balkarian Republic is the pearl of nature in the Russian Federation, and this is confirmed not only by specialists, but by the increasing flow of tourists to the region. Here are just the future of this wonderful republic with the current dynamics of its ecological condition every year more and more alarming.

CONCLUSION:

Summarizing all the above, we find it expedient to designate the following directions for stabilizing the ecological situation in the region:

- environmental technologies, mandatory environmental assessment of new production projects, the creation of non-waste technologies of the closed cycle;

- reasonable self-restraint in the use of natural resources, especially energy sources, which are essential for the life of mankind;
- international conventions on environmental protection, which carry out a variety of joint development and programs.
- strict sanctions and fines at the state level for pollution of the atmosphere, water and land;
- educational work among the population, social advertising.

REFERENCES:

1. Danilov-Danilyan V.I. 2000. Ecological challenge and sustainable development. Moscow, Russia: Progress-Tradition.
2. Ecological Doctrine of the Russian Federation. Russian newspaper. 09.18.2002.
3. Alborov I.D. 2012. State of the Environment of the North Caucasus: Problems and Solutions. North Ossetia, Russia.
4. Bokoev E.A. 2017. Acute environmental problems of the North Caucasian Federal District. North Ossetia, Russia.
5. Magomedov A. Sh., Musaeva T.M. The main environmental problems of Makhachkala. Young Scientist. 2018; 2: 128-130.
6. Pankova E.B. "We are sick twice as often." How do industry giants affect health? Arguments and Facts. North Caucasus, 2017; 48.
7. Tavasiev V.Kh., Tavasiev G.V. Economic and social-environmental problems of urban settlements of the Republic of North Ossetia-Alania. Basic research, 2015; 11-7: 1489-1492.